
PROJECT FEASIBILITY STUDY AND ANALYSIS IN AQUACULTURE

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ABSTRACT

This paper reviews the process of fisheries and aquaculture projects feasibility studies, reports and feasibility analysis. This is to be seen as part of the larger effort in the quest for food fish security in Nigeria. The focus was on human capacity building in the subject matter. There is a great need for the development of local capacity on small-scale, medium-scale and large-scale project feasibility study, reports and feasibility analysis in order to realize and sustain the set target in the fishery sub-sector of the Agricultural Transformation Agenda (ATA) of present administration in view of the fast growing aquaculture industry in Nigeria. The important roles of project feasibility study and analysis as the initial stages in the development of aquaculture projects were reviewed under the following sub-headings: site selection survey, feasibility report, and feasibility analysis. The importance of proper site selection studies prior to approval of a proposed location and site, and confirmation of economic viability prior to adoption of a proposed project cannot be over emphasized. The main aim is to ensure that, as its contribution to the overall national development efforts, investment decisions and actions in fisheries and aquaculture sub-sector are based on well formulated and environmentally friendly projects.

KEYWORDS: Aquaculture, projects, feasibility study, feasibility analysis, national development plans, clean environment.

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INTRODUCTION

The total local fish production in Nigeria currently stands at 700,000 tons per annum while average importation is estimated at some 800,000 tons per annum. However, projected demand for fish in Nigeria stands at about 3 million tons, suggesting actual shortfall of 1.5 million or 50% of the estimated demand (Odusote, 2013). In 2010, the total aquaculture investment and capital contribution in Nigeria were put at N7 billion and N20 billion respectively (Faturoti, 2010). This figure is considered encouraging but much more is expected from aquaculture production in Nigeria. The fishery sub-sector of agricultural transformation agenda under the chairmanship of President Goodluck Jonathan and the stewardship of Dr Akinwunmi Adesina, the Honourable Minister of agriculture, has set a transformation target for the increased and sustainable production of 1 million tons of aquaculture fish per annum for the next 5 years (Odusote, 2013). In 2010 alone a total of 340 students from various universities, polytechnics and colleges of education across Nigeria were in ARAC for their 6 months supervised industrial work experience (SIWES) program (Opara *et al.*, 2010). Majority of these students lacked the necessary skills in project formulation and analysis. These young students are the future leaders of our dear country, Nigeria and as such they should be well equipped with the necessary skills in project formulation and analysis early in their academic training. There is, therefore, a great need for the development of the local capacity on small-scale, medium-scale and large-scale project planning and analysis, feasibility studies and feasibility analysis, project preparation, and appraisal even at undergraduate levels to realize and sustain the target of food fish security in the fishery sub-sector of the Agricultural Transformation Agenda (ATA) of President Goodluck Jonathan's administration.

This paper reviews the current feasibility studies and feasibility analysis techniques as planning and preparation stages of aquaculture projects. The main focus is on three key reports namely the site selection survey report, the

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comprehensive economic feasibility report, and the feasibility analysis report which are generally written as part of project formulation. The overall aim is to ensure that aquaculture project investment decisions and actions are based on well informed knowledge of the prevailing technical and economic environments of the proposed site.

Definition

Aquaculture project feasibility study is essentially locational, biotechnical, economic, social and cultural investigations of a proposed location, site and host community of a proposed project with a view to addressing a specific problem. On the other hand, project feasibility reports describe one or more solutions to a specific problem and determine if the solution proposed is technically and institutionally feasible, financially viable, socio-culturally acceptable and economically justified. They document all thought processes relating to a solution to a problem or task, a description of the solution, and reasons why that solution should be implemented. Managers need accurate and comprehensive feasibility reports to make sound decisions regarding where and where not to commit scarce resources. In addition, an accurate and comprehensive feasibility report helps in developing other documents such as formal proposal, specifications, work plans and time lines.

Classification of Feasibility Studies

In aquaculture project feasibility studies can be classified into simple and complex types. Simple feasibility studies are for projects which are extensive or semi-intensive in nature and do not involve any integration whereas complex types are intensive, or hyper-intensive in nature as well as projects involving one or more integration in terms of feeding, stocking rate and management practice. In aquaculture project feasibility studies may also be classified based on the components of the various reports that may be lumped under the general term feasibility study as follows:

1. Strategy study: selection of objectives, tactics, and decision criteria.
2. Market analysis: Economic base studies or other related aggregate data review.
3. Merchandising studies: consumer surveys, competitive property analysis, marketability evaluation, etc.
4. Legal studies: Opinion on potential legal constraints, model contracts or forms of organization, and political briefs.
5. Compatibility studies: Project and community planning, conservation standards, on other public policies.
6. Engineering: land planning, and architectural studies.
7. Financial studies: Economic modeling, capital budgets, present value and discounted cash-flow forecasts, rate of return analysis, other financial packages.

THE PROCESS OF PROJECT FEASIBILITY STUDIES IN AQUACULTURE

Site Selection Studies:

Not all locations and sites are suitable for sitting a specific aquaculture project. The success of an aquaculture project for example earthen pond fish farms, therefore, depends to a large extent on the proper selection of the site to be developed into fish farms (Uzukwu, 2010b) The site selected must be locationally, biotechnically, financially, socio-culturally and economically feasible. Factors to be considered are primarily the environmental, biotechnical and socio-economic factors on the site during the rainy and dry seasons.

FRAMEWORK FOR SITE SELECTION SURVEY IN AQUACULTURE

The framework for comprehensive development of site selection survey in aquaculture provides for identification of factors, existing constraints in the site which can make or mar the profitability of the project in the following subject matter (Uzukwu, 2010b):

ENVIRONMENTAL FACTORS

- a) Water Supply (sources, quantity, quality)
 - Must be of sufficient quantity in terms of discharge or yield
 - Pond drainage should be possible
 - Pollution risk should be taken into account
 - Flood risk should be considered

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- Tide levels (tidal range) should be adequate for tidal ponds
 - Wave action should be taken into account
 - Silt, petroleum, pesticides, radio nuclides, etc, risks in tidal water supply should be considered
 - Water source must be optimum in quality with reference to physical, chemical and biological properties
 - Environmental concerns for safe discharge of effluents
- b) Nature of Land
- Slope of land ,that is, not steeper than 2.30%
 - Ground elevation with reference to water source should not promote flooding
 - Vegetation should not be too dense
 - Space for expansion if necessary should be available
 - Site should be free of right of way (ROW) of pipelines, pylons and masts.
 - Perimeter and topographic survey maps of site should be available
- c) Soil Type and properties
- Identify soil type (pervious, impervious or peaty)
 - Soil should be able to retain water
 - A sandy clay to clay loam is best soil
 - The coefficient of permeability should range from 5×10^{-6} m/s to 1×10^{-4} m/s
 - Soil pH should range from 6.5 to 8.5
 - Soil should be fertile in terms of N.P.K.
- d) Climate and Watershed
- Climatic factors to be considered are temperature, rainfall, evaporation, sunshine, wind speed and direction, and relative humidity

BIOTECHNICAL FACTORS

- Fish species selection/diversity(Anyanwu, 2006; Ansa, 2012)
- Availability of seeds
- Type of project
 - small scale
 - medium scale
 - large scale
- Culture intensity
 - extensive
 - semi-intensive
 - intensive
 - hyper intensive
- Culture Method
 - monoculture
 - monosex culture
 - polyculture
 - integrated culture
- Culture System
 - Static water system - extensive/semi-intensive
 - Flow through system - semi-intensive/intensive
 - Water recirculation system - intensive/hyper intensive

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- Production target- how many tons of fish per annum will be produced

SOCIO-ECONOMIC FACTORS

- Availability of market
- Transport
- Availability and cost of labour
- Suitability of management plan
- Government policy
- Legal matters
- Law and order
- Social conflict
- Funds

Then follow the design of the pond and/or tank systems and the farm support facilities.

The pond /tank system to be designed comprises the various pond compartments with various uses such as production pond ,transition pond , nursery pond, brood stock pond and quarantine pond as well as the oxygen supply and water inlet and drainage structures: monk, sluice gate, pipes, culverts, canals, etc.

The support facilities to be designed include farm building, farm roads, road dykes, storage shed (for feeds and equipment), security and sales offices, hatchery complex, feed mill, power house, portable water supply for the operators, etc.

The financial and economic analysis, with emphasis on the indices of project profitability, viability and sustainability would naturally follow.

Market Survey

An important aspect of feasibility studies for aquaculture is market survey for: the existing fish market, the price pattern, the preference and biases, the existing sources of fish supply (level of competition), the elasticity of demand pattern for fish, the cost of labour and services, etc. The market survey is important in the preparation of capital costs, running costs, projected revenue and benefits to be expected (Uzukwu, 2010a; Uzukwu *et al.*, 2010). Projections for the future are usually made with an allowance of 5-10% inflationary trend in view (Uzukwu, 1996).

THE FEASIBILITY REPORT

The aim of feasibility studies is to obtain relevant data needed to confirm the rationale for selecting the chosen site and project option. The feasibility report will be the basis on which managers will prepare the proposals which analysts will work on to decide whether to support or reject the project. In other words, project appraisal and investment decision are based on the feasibility report. It provides preliminary designs and cost estimates for the project, based on considerable data gathering and analysis. Finally, all probable impacts are considered and a conclusion is drawn regarding the economic feasibility of the project.

STRUCTURE AND CONTENT OF A FEASIBILITY REPORT

Most feasibility reports contain the following elements:

- i. Executive Summary: In the summary the main results of the feasibility study are summarized for individuals without the time or need to read the entire report.
- ii. An abstract: that includes a short summary of the conclusions and recommendations made.
- iii. An introduction: That presents the context of the fishery demand and supply situation and gives a clear and concise statement of the problem to be solved. Also included here are the description of the project area/location and profile of the promoter(s).
- iv. Description of project site (environmental) conditions with emphasis on water supply (quantity and quality, flood risks, aquatic pollution risks), soil quality, topography, fish species selection, availability of fish seeds, and socio-economic settings.

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- v. Description of the production process(es) to be adopted including the design criteria and specifications. The design of the pond and tank systems and all the support facilities are also included here. The proposed culture system is aptly captured here also.
- vi. The Financial Analysis: The capital cost, the operating (running) cost and the projected revenue give a detailed description of the total cost implication of the project and the projected revenue profile. Also included here are the results of the computation of the indices of project viability such as pay-back period, return on capital investment, the internal rate of return, (IRR) and the profitability index (PI) (Uzukwu, 1996; Uzukwu *et al.*, 2010). For IRR and PI which are computed using discounted cash flows the preparation of the following tables is imperative: (i) cash flow projection, (ii) projected profit and loss account, (iii) projected balance sheet, (iv) fixed assets and depreciation, (v) statement of cost of sales, (vi) maintenance expenses, and (vii) loan amortization schedule (Uzukwu, 1996).
- vii. Conclusion and Recommendations: For further action and a listing of issues that must be resolved before the project design can be implemented.

A GUIDE TO FEASIBILITY ANALYSIS

The Concept

Project feasibility analysis is the testing of the marketing, legal, financial, physical, and social dimensions of a project. The client who is putting together a deal, in an attempt to solve fish shortage problem, or buying a piece of swampy land has control over only certain variables. He must be compatible with the context of all those factors which he cannot change and which place demands on the solution he seeks. The project formulators seek to identify risk factors and how the project can operate profitably in the context of those risks factors. Context defines the problem, feasibility report gives the proposed solution, and feasibility analysis is concerned with identifying and measuring the decisive elements of fit between the two. Indeed, projects feasibility analysis is primarily a search for a possible cause of project failure or misfit in the project proposal. It represents a source of dissatisfaction or failure to achieve certain goals set. Any project is feasible when the analyst determines that there is a reasonable likelihood of satisfying explicit objectives when a selected course of action is tested for fit to a context of specific constraints and limited resources (Unpublished report).

Framework of Total Feasibility Analysis

The structural framework for comprehensive development of feasibility analysis provides for: identification of objectives, existing constraints and self-imposed standards, and finally alternative lines of action in the following subject matter:

1. Objectives of the stakeholders for whom the feasibility study is carried out:
 - (a) Strategic objectives and priorities
 - (b) Acceptable tactical alternatives
2. Market trends and opportunity areas
 - (a) Aggregate data on local population, employment, disposable income, etc.
 - (b) National economic and political policies affecting incentive, timing risk, etc.
 - (c) Significant popular attitudes and trends
3. Alternative merchandising target or market segments
 - (a) Special micro-markets with space needs
 - (b) Product and price specifications
 - (c) Effective demand for the produce at a price
 - (d) Preferred merchandising methods
4. legal-political constraints and alternatives
 - (a) Regulatory constraints on the stakeholders
 - (b) Regulatory controls on site and space development
 - (c) Exogenous political structure influencing alternatives available.
5. Aesthetic-ethical constraints and alternatives
 - (a) Project relationship to immediate community
 - (b) Project obligations to immediate community
 - (c) Prime contractor-subcontractor relationships
 - (d) Client obligations to his preferred personal commitment pattern.

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6. Physico-technical constraints and alternative
 - (a) Space user requirements as to location and improvements
 - (b) Site attributes satisfying elements of item No. I
 - (c) All other space product engineering considerations.
7. Financial constraints and alternatives
 - (a) Timeline or assured calendar of events for financial assumptions
 - (b) Capital budget required and sources
 - (c) Operating budgets and revenue sources
 - (d) Direct cash profit expectations
 - (e) Indirect benefits and returns
 - (f) Measurement of risks and yields

Frequently the appraiser or feasibility analyst may be required to do only a portion of the total analysis outlined above. However, someone must provide the assumptions in those elements listed prior to financial analysis. Also someone must provide the preliminary objectives on which the feasibility of the project must be based (Unpublished report).

EVALUATION OF SURVEY DATA

The success of any fish farm operations depends not only on the general site suitability for fish production but also on other related factors such biological factors. It is also important in providing valuable information in the preparation of the overall design and layout of the facility, engineering modifications to be made and the choice of management practices appropriate for the given site. No site possesses all the desirable characteristics for fish pond operation. Also, no two sites are exactly identical with one another. Hence, the degree of suitability of various sites evaluated varies from one area to another.

Method of Evaluation

The evaluation of the suitability of fish farm sites involves a detailed survey of both technical and non-technical aspects, and the processing of information gathered in order to make the final selection. Data and information collected during the survey are combination of quantitative and qualitative: thus, it is very difficult to arrive at general decision. The most commonly used method of deciding the suitability of sites from among a number of prospective sites surveyed is the point and ranking system; in which all data and information are assigned numerical points or scores, for example 1-10 or 1-100. A site with the most desirable characteristic for certain criterion is assigned the highest score, the lower the value, the less ideal the site becomes.

There are two ways of assigning points for the different items in the criteria: (1) the unweighted point system which considers every criterion to have equal degree of importance and (ii) the weighted point system which recognizes the varying degree of importance of each criterion by assigning weight or multiplying factors. The latter is considered better than the former. The following weight multiplier for various criteria has been suggested (Uzukwu, 2008):

Table 1. Weight multipliers

S/NO	Criterion	Relative weight
1	Water supply system	4
2	Socio-economic impact	3
3	Accessibly	1
4	Available area	2
5	Water quality	3
6	Soil quality	3
7	Kind of vegetation	0.5
8	Density of vegetation	0.5
9	Elevation (topography)	3
10	Possibility of mechanization	1
11	Protection from winds, waves, tide currents (coastal aquaculture)	1

Table 2: Illustrates the evaluation range for scores earned by each site

S/NO	Range of Scores	Evaluation
1	80 – 100	Excellent site for development
2	60 – 79	Very good
3	40 – 59	Good
4	Below 40	Not worth considering

Table 3. Illustration of the unweighted point system for sites (A,B,C).

Soil Quality

	A	B	C
Top soil depth	4.5	5	10
Textured	30% sand	60% sand	70% sand
pH	6.5	3.5	8.0

Environmental / Climatic factor

	A	B	C
Land elevations (AWSL)	10	5	20
Water supply	5	0.01	0.06
Vegetation	Dense	Sparse	Dense

Water Quality

	A	B	C
pH	7.0	5.0	6.5
Salinity	30%	10%	35%
Pollution	Yes	No	Yes

Other Factors

	A	B	C
Nearness to market (m)	50	20	10
Accessibility	Yes	Yes	Yes
Distance to sources of supplies	10	15	5
Distance to fish seed supply	50	30	10

Table 4. Points earned by the three sites A, B, and C

Soil Quality	A	B	C
Top Soil depth	9	8	4
Texture	7	3	2
pH	9	3	10
Environmental/climatic factor			
Land elevation (AWSL)	8	9	4
Water supply	9	4	6
Vegetation	5	8	5
Water Quality			
pH	10	5	6
Salinity	6	9	5
Pollution Risk	1	8	1
Other Factors			
Nearness to market (m)	5	8	9
Accessibility	8	8	8
Distance to source of supply	7	5	9
Distance to fish seed supply	4	6	8
Total points	88	84	77
Rating (%)	68	65	59

Considering the relatively high scores, all three sites can be considered for fish farm development. Based on ranking, area A is the top scorer followed by B, C is third.

The creative function of the feasibility analyst is to understand the values, objectives and alternative tactics of the parties at interest well enough that the analyst can invent methods of assembling facts about these alternative course of action or consequences which fit both the information available and criteria which apply the objectives and value preference to a choice. A decision machine is only the useful and conscious application in a simplified model form of the methods by which we all make choices. It is a stylized model of behaviour reduced to a point where it is capable of using available information to represent what is a dynamic process relative to project planning questions.

FEASIBILITY REPORT AND PROJECT MANAGEMENT

Project management involves three primary matters:

(i) Planning – organizing the project to succeed through the appropriate and timely allocation of resources to tasks.

(ii) Managing – a means to understand where you are up to and what is next.

(iii) Communicating – a means to keep stakeholders informed of your progress and issues through reports, reviews and documentation. The feasibility report also forms the basis for a sound project management. It defines the objectives, the primary attributes and the most feasible approach for successful implementation using available resources (funds, skills, tools, good will, etc). It also defines the content of the project including the results of studies and thought, what needs to be done, and why, and what will be practically achievable. Armed with the feasibility report, the project manager can easily assess the scope of the project and consider the time line and efforts (approaches) required to achieve a given mile stone in relation to what skills/capabilities that are available or accessible. Finally the feasibility report is a veritable tool for project evaluation (UNEP, 2009).

COSTING FEASIBILITY STUDIES/REPORTS

A general guideline for costing feasibility studies and reports in aquaculture do not exist yet (Uzukwu, 1996). I hereby recommend 1–2% of construction cost. Over the years experience shows that clients do not want to pay for feasibility study/reports as percentage of construction cost. Most clients would want to pay only after the required credit/funding has been secured using the feasibility report. The problem remains, and there is need to borrow a leaf from lawyers who would render service only after payment has been made.

SUMMARY

The process of fisheries and aquaculture projects feasibility studies, reports and feasibility analysis has been reviewed. The importance of proper site selection studies prior to approval of a proposed site, feasibility analysis and confirmation of economic viability prior to adoption of a proposed project are thoroughly treated and strongly recommended. Finally I wish to acknowledge the author of the unauthored, undated reports which were extensively referenced in this article as unpublished report.

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